

IN-SITU OBSERVATION OF DEFORMATION AND FRACTURE PROCESS FOR FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES UNDER SEM

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ABSTRACT

Deformation and fracture behavior of metal matrix composites was studied by means of "in-situ" observation under a Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM). Materials used were unidirectionally fiber reinforced SiC(Nicalon)/Al and C(Torayca)/Al. In-situ observation of three point bending test under SEM provided indications about importance of fiber-matrix interface on crack initiation, arrest and propagation. Fatigue behavior was also studied under SEM.

KEY WORDS: FRM, Aluminum Composites, Scanning Electron Microscopy, In-situ observation, Fracture process, Deformation process, SiC fiber, C fiber, Fatigue, Three point bending test

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the key issues to design and produce high performance fiber reinforced composite materials (FRMs) is to get a clear understanding of fracture process. There have been many research works on this issue both with theoretical and experimental standpoint, but yet to have enough evidence to prove the proposed mechanistic models[1-4]. On the other hand, there have been many progresses in R & D of high performance metal matrix composites (MMCs). One of the significant efforts can be seen in the Japanese National Project on the development of advanced composite materials for the future industries under the guidance of the MITI, Japan[5-8], where SiC(Nicalon) and C(Torayca) fiber reinforced Al matrix composites were successfully developed using wire preforms made by a liquid infiltration method.

This work provides results from direct observation of deformation and fracture process of fiber reinforced composites by means of scanning electron microscopy with a newly designed "in-situ" deformation stage. In this meaning, an acoustic microscopy (SAM) has become one of the most promising methods, owing to significant progresses in acoustic microscopy, especially in spatial resolution. In this paper, mainly from the limitation of the paper length, quite limited information about SAM is provided. Some additional information about In-situ observation results of three point bending test under SAM can be seen in reference 9, where the major issues of concern have been and are crack initiation and propagation characteristics and stress distributions around crack tip.

The final goal of this work is to present models of fracture mechanism for variety of composites based on experimental evidences.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1. Specimens Used

The materials used were PCS-SiC/Al and C/Al. The multi-filament long fibers, PCS-type SiC fibers (Nicalon) and the PAN type carbon fibers (Torayca) were used as reinforcement and pure Al were used as matrix. The composite wires were made with liquid metal infiltration method from the test plants of Nippon Carbon, for SiC/Al, and Toray, for C/Al. The plate materials of the composites were made by hot-rolling method, for SiC/Al, and hot-press method, for C/Al. The specimens were cut out from the plate materials with $2t \times 3w \times 40l$ mm and surfaces for observation were polished to mirror finish using 0.06 mm Al_2O_3 powder. Volume fraction of specimens were 45%, for SiC/Al and 40%, for C/Al[9]. Fiber directions were parallel and perpendicular to the specimen axis, which were denoted as 0° and 90° specimen. The majority of the specimens had a center notch to initiate fracture from the central position of the specimens at the tension side.

2.2. "In-situ" experiment under SEM

A conventional type "In-situ" deformation stage for SEM had been designed and installed to a Hitachi S-510 SEM by one of the authors, N.N.[10], which had capabilities for tensile test, compression test, bending test and scratch test with the loading capability of 200kgf. Utilizing the pre-existing frame, the new computerized motor driven displacement mechanism and higher accuracy stress measurement system were installed. The most important issue to obtain clear SEM image "in-situ" was to suppress vibration and electrical noises during the test[11]. This improvement gave the capabilities to this system for performing precise control of displacement rate and stress patterns which made it possible to test fatigue, creep, and relaxation.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. "In-situ" experiment under SEM

Figure 1 Typical fracture behavior by three point bend test in SiC/Al 0° specimen, under deflections of (A) 0.6mm, (B) 1.2mm and (C) 1.6mm.

3.1.1. SiC/Al 0° specimen

Figure 1 shows the typical fracture behavior observed in a notched SiC/Al 0° specimen which is very similar to that observed in a un-notched specimen. With increasing tensile strain, fiber cracking was taken place (Figure 1 (a)), then opening of cracks in fibers followed (Figure 1 (b)) and the following connecting actions of the cracks through Al matrix (Figure 1 (c)) led to the final fracture. From the stress-strain measurement, the stress where crack initiation in fibers started was evaluated to be nearly a half of the fracture stress and that for crack opening started was about 90% of the fracture stress. The crack opening was taken place by the deformation of matrix adjacent to the fibers which was driven by the stress concentration at the fiber crack tip. This behavior of plastic deformation in matrix near the fiber-matrix interface was similar to those observed in the short fiber reinforced plastics [12] and SiC whisker reinforced Al [13] which is interpreted to be caused by the strong bonding strength between fiber and matrix. This might also be supported by the multiple cracking in fibers with short distance as seen in the Figure 1 (c). SEM fractographs taken after complete fracture showed the existence of mirror fracture surface in many fibers which is indicating that the surface flaw of fibers was a major initiation site of cracks. This is consistent with the results seen in reference 14. Figure 2 provides an example of macroscopic behavior of crack propagation. From this set of pictures, fracture process can be divided into three stages; (1) elastic to plastic deformation to initiate cracks in fibers, (2) opening of cracks in fibers together with initiation of cracks and plastic deformation of matrix and (3) connection of cracks through matrix to the ultimate fracture. This zigzag motion of crack propagation was also seen in the side surface which eliminated the possible cause to produce such fracture path as stress gradient to the through thickness direction. From the same figure, the areal density of surface fiber crack was known to be proportional to the areal fraction of fibers. That is, the area with higher fiber volume fraction produced higher number of cracks which led to the tendency to propagate the main crack dominantly through the area with the higher local fiber volume fraction.

Figera 2 Typical fracture behavior by three point bend test in SiC/Al 0° specimen, under deflections of (A)1.2mm, (B)1.5mm, (C)1.7mm and (D)2.4mm.

In order to analyze fiber - matrix interaction at the stage (2), gold was surface deposited to the specimens and they were tested. The results were categorized into three types as shown in Figure 3. Type-A was characterized by the formation of shear slip band to the direction of maximum shear stress from the crack tip at the fiber surface and type-B was characterized by the crack blunting near the fiber surface. In both cases, deformation was very much restricted, or localized, and was not directly connected with final

Figure 3 Representative types of fracture behavior seen in SiC/Al 0° specimen

mirror fracture surface indicated negative prospects to the case (4). As to the cases (2) and (3), we don't have any data to discuss even qualitatively.

3.1.2. SiC/Al 90° specimen

The typical fracture behavior seen is shown in Figure 4. Figure 4(A) presents the initial appearance and with increasing bending deflection, slip lines were developed in matrix, Figure 4(B), followed by further development of slip lines and initiation of crack near fiber surface, Figure 4(C), and reached to the final fracture. The development of main crack to the final fracture was done by connecting the micro cracks ahead of the main crack and micro cracks were initiated near fiber surface by shear deformation along slip lines. This behavior is very similar to those observed in particulate dispersion strengthened materials. Figure 4 also indicates very much localized deformation behavior by shear slip deformation. The groups of fibers, as marked with filled circles and open circles, were divided by slip lines and within each group their mutual positions did not change under further deformation. The main crack propagated preferentially through areas with high fiber volume fraction. This is suggesting that the stress level in those areas are higher than in other areas and this will be shown by SAM results.

Fracture behavior of un-notched specimen was similar to that of notched specimen, but there was a difference in the position of micro crack initiation. The exfoliation of fiber-matrix interface was generally observed in un-notched specimens as shown in Figure 5, whereas, in

fracture. That is, these cases were seen at relatively low stress level, which was about 75% of the fracture stress, and further development of deformation was hardly seen. Deformation for the case of type-C was initiated at the crack tip at the fiber surface and was developed along the fiber axis very much localized and adjacent to the fiber. The development of type-C took place at relatively high stress level, which was about 90% of the fracture stress, and became a dominant path of the main crack to the final fracture. As origins to cause these fracture behavior, the present results provided the following possibilities.

- (1) Effect of fiber-matrix bonding strength,
- (2) Effect of matrix grain orientation at crack tip,
- (3) Effect of crack propagation velocity,
- (4) Effect of crack propagation orientation in fiber.

The precise analysis of crack propagation orientation in fiber by

Figure 4 Typical fracture behavior by three point bend test in SiC/Al 90° specimen, under deflections of (A) 0mm, (B) 0.2mm, (C) 0.4mm and (D) 0.6mm.

Figure 5 Micro crack formation, exfoliation at fiber surface in the un-notched SiC/Al 90° specimen.

notched specimen, micro crack generation took place near the interface. And the average displacement value to produce micro crack was 3.0 mm and 0.6 mm for un-notched and notched specimens, respectively. This is interpreted to be due to the fact that in the case of notched specimen stress concentration near the notch makes it easy to make slip deformation in matrix with

Figure 6 Typical fracture behavior by three point bend test in C/Al 0° specimen, under deflections of (A) 0mm, (B) 1.9mm, (C) 2.3mm and (D) 2.6mm.

Figure 7 Fracture behavior observed in gold deposited C/Al 0° specimen, under deflections of (A) 1.0mm, (B) 1.3mm and (C) 1.5mm.

relatively low interfacial stress, thus little exfoliation was generated. This is also suggesting that improvement of interfacial strength may result in improvement of mechanical property of the composite and for evaluating interfacial strength under tensile stress three point bend test utilizing un-notched 90° specimen is effective.

3.1.3. C/Al 0° specimen

The C/Al composites used in this study were applied Ti-B double CVD coating to carbon fibers and this made interfacial bonding strength very weak[6]. As a result, fiber was broken first, and followed by fiber pull-outs. The successive plastic deformation in matrix led to the final fracture. This can be seen in Figure 6. The precise inspections were done by utilizing gold deposited specimens. Figure 7 shows the early part of fiber pull-outs, where no slip lines nor indication of plastic deformation can be identified. This is one of the significant differences from SiC/Al composites reflecting the

Figure 8 Slip lines observed in matrix of gold deposited C/Al 0° specimen.

difference in interfacial bonding strength. Following to the fiber fracture and pull-outs, slip lines were generated in matrix. The slip lines were developed as those observed in single crystal deformation, which is shown in Figure 8. In the case of the C/Al used in this study, matrix grains behaved like single crystals and the strength of the composites stayed near around the simple rule of mixture value. The one reason of this was the weak interfacial bonding strength and thus the preferential crack propagation path through areas with higher fiber density observed in SiC/Al was not observed.

These results suggest the importance to maintain original fiber strength during the whole process to produce final composite products. Although, some results indicated the degrading mechanisms of composite strength by residual stress and by interfacial reaction zone formation, these will be discussed elsewhere [15].

3.1.4. C/Al 90° specimen

Fracture behavior in notched C/Al 90° specimen, as shown in Figure 9, can be classified as follows.

(1) micro crack generation by exfoliation between fiber and matrix

Exfoliation between fiber and matrix took place before plastic deformation of matrix was taken place and became micro cracks which was the initial stage of the fracture process. Almost all exfoliation took place in the longitudinal direction of specimen which tensile stress was applied (crack direction was perpendicular to the tensile axis).

(2) connection of micro cracks

Fracture progressed as micro cracks were connected each other through matrix. Main crack was initiated from the bottom of the notch and was propagated by connecting the nearest micro crack. The connection was done by shear fracture between the crack tip of the main crack and that of nearest micro crack by so-called un-zipping mechanism. The tensile strength to this fiber direction was 44MPa and 100MPa for C/Al and SiC/Al, respectively. This difference was mainly due to the difference in interfacial bonding strength. These results suggest the importance to increase interfacial bonding strength and to homogenize the fiber distribution to reduce fiber localization. Because highly localized fiber distributions are thought to provide short path for crack propagation at lower stress level.

3.1.5. Fatigue behavior in SiC/Al

Figure 9 Fracture behavior observed in C/Al 90° specimen, under deflections of (A)0.42mm, (B)0.43mm, (C)0.45mm and (D)0.47mm.

Figure 10 High cycle fatigue fracture surface in SiC/Al 0° specimen.

Fatigue behavior was investigated both by sequential SEM observation during fatigue test out of the "in-situ" stage and by "in-situ" observation in the stage. At the stress between elastic limit and the initiation of fiber fracture, fatigue crack was initiated from the bottom of the notch and extended along fiber surfaces. No fiber fracture was observed up to 20,000 stress cycles. The final fracture surface indicated the fatigue crack generation along fibers before the fatigue limit which resulted in many long fiber pull-out as shown in Figure 10. There was no striation observed in the fracture surface. While at higher stress levels, within the range of low cycle fatigue regime, slip line development was observed successively to produce striations at fracture surface. Type-A crack propagation shown in Figure 3 was mainly observed in the case of low cycle fatigue fracture and crack propagate was dominantly along fiber direction with very much localized deformation area. Figure 11 is an example, where the characteristic features mentioned the above can be seen. In the case of SiC/Al 90° specimen, the fatigue fracture behavior was basically the same as that for the case of SiC/Al 90° specimen. The major differences from the static fracture test (see 3.1.2.) were the formation of interfacial exfoliation which could only be observed in un-notched specimens by three point bend test and the suppression of slip line formation. These results suggest the effectiveness of this testing method for obtaining the clear understandings of fatigue behavior in FRMs and further study is under way.

4. CONCLUSION

"In-situ" observation of fracture process in FRMs was carried out using special stages designed and equipped

Figure 11 Low cycle fatigue fracture surface in SiC/Al 0° specimen.

with a SEM. The results obtained from the experiments supplementarily provided information about fracture process in FRMs as follows.

1) In SiC/Al 0° specimens, fiber fracture by bend test was taken place preferentially in the areas with higher fiber volume fraction. Whereas, in SiC/Al 90° specimens, localized deformation in matrix dominated by shear slip was observed in highly fiber distributed areas. These behavior can be related with the strong interfacial bonding strength in SiC/Al.

2) In C/Al 0° specimens, debonding of fiber and matrix happened prior to the fiber fractures and matrix deformation was similar with that in a single crystal. Whereas, in SiC/Al 90° specimens, micro cracks near interface were connected by un-zipping mechanism and in the specimens without notches, micro crack formation at the interface, exfoliation of matrix from fibers, was observed. These behavior is closely related with the weak bonding strength in C/Al.

3) Fatigue behavior in SiC/Al was strongly stress dependent and in the case of high cycle fatigue regime, fatigue crack formation dominated along fiber surface and in the case of low cycle fatigue regime, localized fatigue crack growth along major slip direction was observed. fracture surfaces had a feature to have striations.

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